

ISSUES OF STUDYING PERSONAL HYGIENE AMONG YOUTH STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7958056>

Abstract. *The lifestyle of a person, his sanitary literacy, the ability to manage himself, his body and, ultimately, his health, are the most important conditions for maintaining health, physical and mental activity, and increasing life expectancy. In other words, the health of each particular person depends primarily on the way of life and the conscious attitude towards him of the person himself, the personality. In this regard, it should be said that the basis of a healthy lifestyle is the knowledge by each person of those factors that are capable of influencing the body in one way or another, and be able to use them for good, and not for harm. In other words, the modern concept of "personal hygiene" is very different from the previously existing one.*

Keywords: *issues, studying, personal, hygiene, among, youth, students.*

Relevance. Today, personal hygiene is the observance by each person of certain hygiene rules in all the diverse aspects of everyday life. Without a doubt, there are many environmental factors of an objective nature that are beyond the control of one person. But at the same time, a hygienically literate person is able to create for himself an environment that allows him to ensure health and longevity. Each person is subject to the regulation of such factors as nutrition, daily routine, working and rest conditions, body hygiene, clothing, housing, hardening and physical culture, giving up bad habits, creating a favorable psychological climate in the family and at work, optimizing people's relationships, etc. Only when the correct assessment of the role of these factors and the ability to use them for the benefit of one's own health becomes part of the general culture of each person, we can expect a decrease in the level of the most common diseases today. In connection with the above, it must be emphasized that the formation of a healthy lifestyle for people is one of the most important tasks of healthcare in any country. At the same time, a healthy lifestyle implies, first of all, the activity, activity of an individual, a group of people, a society that uses material and spiritual conditions and opportunities in the interests of health, harmonious physical and spiritual development of a person. Healthcare in our country, which has become a social system, is an important, but not the only factor in a healthy lifestyle, reflecting all aspects of lifestyle. Studies of domestic and foreign scientists have reliably shown that in a number of influences that determine the state of health, or rather ill health, pathology, i.e. risk factors, the first place is occupied by an unhealthy lifestyle, moreover, health directly depends on it. The share of lifestyle factors exceeds 50% of all conditioning influences. Further, up to about 20% is occupied by hereditary factors and environmental pollution, and about 10% is accounted for by defects, shortcomings and other negative phenomena in the work of health authorities and institutions. So, speaking about the way of life, first of all, one must bear in mind the organic

connection of this concept with the concept of behavior in the broad sense of the word, as an active, active principle that depends on the individual. The subject as the subjective side of society.

The purpose of the study. was to substantiate the specific characteristics of a healthy lifestyle of young people on the example of students of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. The research was carried out by the method of questioning among students (1-2 and 3 courses) of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. According to the age composition, students are distributed as follows: 1 group 18-20; 2nd group 20-24 and 3rd group 24-28 years old. Analysis of the questionnaire survey "How do you rate your health?" Boys and girls equally believe that their health is good (88%, 80% and 89% among 3 age groups). Accordingly, the 1st group 80%, the second 84% and the third 92% know about the rules of a healthy lifestyle. At the next stage of the work, the peculiarities of the nutrition of students were studied. Rational nutrition is one of the main conditions for a healthy lifestyle. It is rational to consider only such nutrition, in which all the components of the products are combined and meet the needs of a person, depending on his age, physiological state and profession. However, not all students comply with the requirements of proper nutrition. To the question "Do they adhere to proper nutrition, the students noted the following: Students of the 1st group adhere to proper nutrition (40%). The second group adhere to proper nutrition (53%). Among the 3 groups adhere to proper nutrition (60%). When asked how many liters of water they drink per day, all age categories noted that they drink about 1-1.5 liters. water per day (60%). According to the results of a study among students on the use of various drinks, we obtained the following data: at the age of 18 to 20 years, Coco-Cola is often consumed (42%). In the second group, girls often drink juice (37%), the male half more often coffee (60%). The third group uses tea more often (90%) To the question "How often do you use fast food?" All age categories do not regularly consume fast food, many (85%) answered a couple of times a month. To the question "Do you use medication?" All groups answered that they use medicines rarely and very rarely (78.2%). An important question for young people is that "Do they go in for physical culture and sports?" Men aged 18-20, 20-24 go in for physical culture and sports up to 61.5%. The third group up to 28%. All 3 groups of the female half answered rarely and very rarely, due to lack of time. The health of young people is largely influenced by the psychological microclimate in the family and the team. To the question "Are you under stress?" Among students in all age categories, girls noted that they often experience stress (58%). Men group 1 47.5%, groups 2 and 3 from 40% to 38%, respectively. But it should be noted that in all age categories, the smoking rate among the male half does not have a sharp difference, amounting to 27.2% to 30.5%. Girls of all age groups answered this question that they are supporters of a healthy lifestyle, maintaining and maintaining their own health and opponents of habits such as smoking, drug addiction. Groups 1 and 2 use of alcoholic beverages is less than 5%. In the third group, the use of alcoholic beverages more often, mainly on holidays, up to 60% of cases. In all age groups, representatives of both sexes have a negative attitude towards drugs (96.8%). The rest did not answer this question. In this case, the integrity of understanding the problems of forming a healthy lifestyle of young people. To the question "Compliance with the sleep regimen", All age categories answered that they sleep 6-8 hours a day (77.4%), that is, they try to get enough sleep and not overwork. To the question "How do you prefer to relax?" The male half noted that they prefer to rest. The female half tries to be more outdoors, in nature, go in for sports.

Conclusions. According to the result of the work carried out, the following can be distinguished: students are well aware of what may pose a threat to their life and health; among

the dominant negative factors, they single out improper and irregular nutrition and physical inactivity. When analyzing the factors hindering the maintenance of a healthy lifestyle, it is clear that the most common response among boys and girls is “lack of free time”, “family problems”, “violation of the norms of a healthy lifestyle on my part”.

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